

Measuring crop diversification in case of sugarcane in West Bengal

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Abstract

In India, diversification towards horticulture was mainly recognised in the 1990s. Crop diversification is a risk management strategy for the farming community and an important step for poverty alleviation and transition from subsistence agriculture to commercial agriculture. Crop diversification is a solution to stabilise and raise farm income, increase employment opportunities, boost exports and conserve and enhance natural resource base. Diversification may be broadly defined as a shift of resources from low value added agriculture to high value added agriculture. In order to measure crop diversification for a particular crop, different types of Crop Diversification Indices (CDI) are used. The CDI is an index of concentration and has a direct relationship with diversification such that a zero value indicates specialization and a value greater than zero signifies crop diversification. The extent of crop diversification at a given point of time may be examined by several indices. Among these indices, Herfindahl Index (HI), Simpson Index (SI) and Entropy Index (EI) are widely used in case of crop diversification. In this paper we want to see whether crop diversification or crop concentration takes place in case of sugarcane in different districts of West Bengal by using secondary data. That's why we consider Herfindahl Index (HI) and Simpson Index (SI) to measure crop diversification or crop concentration in different parts of West Bengal by using secondary data.

Keywords: *Crop diversification, crop concentration, Herfindahl Index (HI) and Simpson Index (SI).*

JEL Classification—C23, R14, Q15

1. Introduction

By crop diversification we mean the addition of new crops or cropping system to agricultural production on a particular form. It takes into account

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the different returns from value added crops with complementary marketing opportunities. Crop diversification gives us a wider choice in the production of a variety of crops in a given area so that production of various crops can be expanded and risk will be reduced considerably. In India crop diversification is generally viewed as a shift from traditionally grown less remunerative crops to more remunerative crops. Crop diversification and growing of large number of crops are taking place in India mainly in the dry land areas to reduce the risk factor of crop failures due to recurring droughts. Crop diversification programme is a sub scheme of Rashtriya Krishi Vikash Yojana (RKVY). This programme was first implemented in 2013-14 in Punjab, Haryana and western Uttar Pradesh where the impact of green revolution was high. The objective of the programme was to diversity from water guzzling crops like paddy to alternative crops like maize, pulses, oil seeds, cotton and agro foresting plantation. Crop diversification is a strategy which tries to enhance and stabilize agricultural productivity. Under this crop diversification programme assistance is provided to the states for conducting cluster demonstration on alternative crops, promotion of water saving technology, distribution of farm machinery, awareness generation, training programme etc.

In India, diversification towards horticulture was mainly recognised in the 1990s. India's average yield of cereal per hectare is less compared to many low income countries. Bangladesh, Vietnam, Indonesia etc. are in a better position than India in case of rice yield. India is lagging much behind China. Both rice yield and wheat yield of India are lowered compared to the global average level. There is also an inter-regional variation in respect of yield of rice and wheat. In some states like Punjab, Haryana etc. the yield of rice and wheat is remarkably high compared to other states. In some states yield is very low. It is not only due to the non-availability of improved technologies but also due to varied agro climatic condition, weather extremities.

It was accompanied with the introduction of economic reforms and the liberalisation of the economy. India is the largest producer of rice in the world. The production of wheat is also enormous. But the productivity of rice and wheat are much lower compared to some other countries. Now Indian economy has slowly diversified from the production of food crops to the non-food crops like cotton, sugarcane etc. The area of production under the non-food crops are rising fast compared to the food crops sector. In

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India, the diversification towards horticulture has mostly been toward the fruits and vegetables. This is happened due to changes in demand. The consumption pattern of the people has changed. So, the demand for fruits and vegetables also changed. Moreover, the rate of return from the horticulture sector is very high. The productivity of fruits and vegetables are much higher compared to the other food crops. Due to these reasons diversification towards horticulture sector is taking place in India. Now India is the largest producer of fruits and vegetables in the world. So now in India horticulture sector is continuously increasing and at the same time the production of food grains is also at the satisfactory level. In this situation it is beneficial for India to experiment diversification towards horticulture sector because it increases national income of the country.

Thus, there is need for crop diversification like cultivation of pulses for stabilising the yield of wheat and paddy in the system. India's average yield of cereal per hectare is far less than that of many countries (including several low income countries), but the difference is huge when compared to China.¹

Further, there is a huge inter-regional variation. The yield of wheat and rice in Haryana and Punjab is much higher than the other states. Low crop yields cannot be attributed to 'non availability' of improved technologies but several factors like varied agro-climatic conditions, weather extremities are responsible for this.²

In this paper to examine whether crop diversification or crop concentration is taking place or not in case of sugarcane in different districts of West Bengal we calculate Herfindahl index and Simpson's index in different time periods. Compound Growth Rates (%) of Area of High value crops of districts of West Bengal between the periods 1997 - 98 to 2004 - 05 is also measured.

2. Objective of the study

In this paper we want to see whether crop diversification or crop concentration takes place in case of sugarcane in different districts of West Bengal by using secondary data. That's why we want to calculate the values of Herfindahl Index (HI) and Simpson Index (SI) to measure crop diversification or crop concentration in case of sugarcane in West Bengal in different time periods. We will also measure the Compound Growth Rates (%) of Area of High value crops of districts of West Bengal from the period

1997 -98 to 2004 -05.

3. Literature survey

Many economists have studied on different aspects of crop diversification in different parts of India. Among them the studies done by Raj Kumar Kundu and Apurba Kumar Chattopadhyay (2018), S. Dasgupta and S.K.Bhaumik (2014), Utpal Kumar De and Manabendu Chattopadhyay (2010), Saumya Chakrabarti and Anirban Kundu (2009) and Utpal Kumar De (2000) are most important.

4. Methodology

In this paper we want to see whether crop diversification or crop concentration takes place in case of sugarcane in different districts of West Bengal by using secondary data. Crop diversification may be broadly defined as a shift of resources from low value agriculture to high value agriculture. In order to measure crop diversification for a particular crop, different types of Crop Diversification Indices (CDI) are used.³ The CDI is an index of concentration and has a direct relationship with diversification such that a zero value indicates complete specialization and a value greater than zero signifies crop diversification. The extent of crop diversification at a given point of time may be examined by several indices. Among these indices, Herfindahl Index (HI) and Simpson Index (SI) are widely used in case of crop diversification.⁴ These indices are computed on the basis of proportion of gross cropped area under different crops cultivated in a particular geographical area. Here Herfindahl Index is the index of concentration.⁵ Higher value of HI represents the specialisation of crop activities. So to obtain the index of diversification, it is subtracted from one, which is the simplified form of Simpson's Index of diversification.

Let us now discuss the different indices of crop diversification.

(i) Herfindahl Index (HI)

The Herfindahl Index is a measure of concentration. It is bounded by zero and one. It takes a value one when complete specialization and approaches to zero when there is diversification of crops.

Herfindahl Index (HI) = $1 - \sum S_i^2$

$$\text{Where } S_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i}$$

Where S_i = Proportion of i^{th} crop

A_i = Area Under i^{th} crop

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$$\sum_{i=1}^n A_i = \text{total cropped area}$$

Here $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ (number of crops)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Here CDI} &= 1 - S_i^2 \\ &= 1 - \text{HI} \end{aligned}$$

It should be noted that the Herfindahl index is the index of concentration and thus the higher value is an indication of specialization of crop activities. Therefore, to obtain the index of diversification, it is subtracted from one.

(ii) Simpson Index (SI)

It is the most suitable index for measuring diversification of crop in a particular geographical region. The formula of Simpson index is given by:-

$$\text{Simpson Index (SI)} = 1 - p_i^2$$

$$\text{Where } P_i = \frac{A_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i}$$

$A_i = \text{Area Under } i^{\text{th}} \text{ crop}$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n A_i = \text{total cropped area}$$

If SI tends to zero, then it indicates that the zone or region is near to the specialization in growing of a particular crop and if it is close to one, then it indicates that the zone is fully diversified in terms of crops.

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5. Empirical Results

Table 1A. Herfindahl Index for crop diversification and crop concentration in case of sugarcane in the various districts of West Bengal in different time periods

Districts	1970-71 to 1972-73	1980-81 to 1982-83	1990-91 to 1992-93	2002-03 to 2004-05	2010 -11 to 2012- 13
Burdwan	0.447046	0.451998	0.354853	0.308771	0.328859
Birbhum	0.404933	0.558101	0.451138	0.374734	0.354864
Bankura	0.530033	0.616401	0.44467	0.426353	0.414358
Midnapur	0.547707	0.567456	0.401684	0.333887	0.345679
Howrah	0.453939	0.422594	0.312999	0.276231	0.346233
Hoogly	0.293613	0.284483	0.240202	0.216166	0.243468
24 Parganas	0.498585	0.464026	0.410005	0.301096	0.281078
Nadia	0.166043	0.129269	0.117529	0.102609	0.142687
Murshidabad	0.154427	0.144391	0.145644	0.135013	0.175986
Dinajpur	0.270857	0.278453	0.325341	0.231396	0.221875
Malda	0.513039	0.524224	0.519643	0.485166	0.465098
Jalpaiguri	0.275346	0.23906	0.218861	0.126001	0.154329
Cooch Behar	0.29553	0.286581	0.284304	0.244563	0.234324
Darjeeling	0.141352	0.141328	0.112184	0.050726	0.046432
Purulia	0.632713	0.685191	0.619696	0.658523	0.628576
West Bengal	0.315714	0.327538	0.282261	0.240207	0.326543

Source: Statistical Abstract, West Bengal (various issues).

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Table: 1B. Herfindahl Index for crop diversification and crop concentration in case of sugarcane in the various districts of West Bengal in different time periods (Graphical presentation)

Source: Statistical Abstract, West Bengal (various issues).

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Table: 2A. Simpson's Index for crop diversification in case of sugarcane in the various districts of West Bengal for different periods

Districts	SUB period I (TE 1990-93)	SUB period II (TE 2000-03)	SUB period III (TE 2010-13)
Nadia	0.84	0.86	0.86
Murshidabad	0.81	0.85	0.84
Malda	0.8	0.82	0.82
Jalpaiguri	0.61	0.8	0.82
24Parganas (North)	0.71	0.8	0.8
Darjeeling	0.69	0.8	0.79
Hooghly	0.7	0.78	0.78
Dinajpur	0.63	0.74	0.76
Cooch Bihar	0.71	0.72	0.73
Howrah	0.56	0.68	0.68
Midnapur	0.52	0.65	0.67
Burdwan	0.58	0.68	0.65
East Midnapur	0.53	0.63	0.63
Birbhum	0.45	0.63	0.63
Bankura	0.49	0.58	0.63
24Parganas (South)	0.26	0.52	0.58
Purulia	0.28	0.39	0.35
West Bengal	0.66	0.76	0.77

Sources:

1. District Statistical Hand Books (Various issues), Bureau of Applied Economics and Statistics, West Bengal.
2. Different issues of 'Estimates of area and production of principle crops' in West Bengal, Directorate of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal.

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Table: 2B Simpson’s Index for crop diversification in case of sugarcane in the various districts of West Bengal for different time periods (Graphical presentation)

Sources:

1. District Statistical Hand Books (Various issues), Bureau of Applied Economics and Statistics, West Bengal.
2. Different issues of 'Estimates of area and production of principle crops' in West Bengal, Directorate of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal.

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Table 3A.

Compound Growth Rates (%) of Area of High value crops of Districts of West Bengal between the periods 1997- 98 to 2004- 05

CROPS	DAR	JAL	COO	DINAJ	MAL	MUR	NAD	24P	HOOG	HOW	PUR	MIDN	BAN	BIR	BUR
TAMATO	33	104	24	77	44	41	125	87	89	99	215	112	57	66	132
ONION	85	24	46	50	62	36	54	39	126	146	235	63	49	64	40
CABBAGE	21	49	30	33	84	16	42	50	62	64	137	127	58	54	80
GARDEN PEES	16	23	25	191	32	37	59	94	67	58	164	37	37	78	700
LADIES FINGER	25	52	17	73	44	47	34	77	108	86	155	26	59	83	37
BRINJAL	18	42	29	38	45	21	29	41	63	36	118	76	24	33	76
BEANS	29	96	35	26	68	18	24	97	45	96	126	14	97	71	45
CAULIFLOWER	33	41	53	109	61	23	29	42	88	49	26	76	77	61	142
CUCERBIT	15	30	27	23	41	21	40	29	24	59	52	47	39	36	23
RADISH	27	57	32	88	134	22	111	74	67	53	57	64	37	50	111
OTHER VEG	24	24	26	16	36	16	28	43	35	26	17	38	45	23	25
GINGER	3	227	54	20	30	66	144	128	160	415	194	49	168	64	94
TURMERIC	58	43	53	55	45	25	50	34	107	102	40	45	49	134	59
SPICES	50	90	0	0	51	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	0	0
MANGO	36	45	42	99	11	21	73	1101	14	48	32	42	50	71	32
JACKFRUIT	89	9	16	32	37	9	12	554	27	60	69	20	229	46	40
PINEAPPLE	39	3	-7	-15	0	0	3387	455	527	505	95	416	0	0	334
ORANGGE ETC.	91	23	48	131	62	62	96	48	79	33	73	24	119	233	128
BANANA	53	33	41	138	81	56	310	74	22	24	53	20	174	45	58
GUAVA	111	168	60	121	68	82	321	-85	131	103	58	53	185	95	115
LICHI	685	17	64	164	256	70	112	278	116	101	50	140	0	833	125
SPETA	0	435	73	114	467	0	700	71	1006	528	16	72	0	335	0
PAPAYA	133	54	45	181	135	-35	141	219	30	10	69	46	216	63	99
COCONUT	0	27	29	100	68	75	109	80	284	0	62	0	473	130	0
CASHEWNUT	37	69	0	0	0	0	136	291	87	68	74	0	115	153	0
OTHER FRUIT	-39	68	85	3631	90	171	119	28	214	180	39	-22	252	135	202
ROSE	86	0	0	0	0	0	82	32	0	32	0	25	0	0	0
TUBE ROSE	0	0	0	0	0	0	196	19	0	22	0	10	0	0	0
GLADIOLIS	20	1400	0	0	0	0	191	112	0	1820	0	27	0	0	0
CRYSANTHEMUM	61	0	0	0	0	0	107	64	0	21	0	70	0	0	0
MARIEGOLD	0	2400	100	0	0	5800	91	644	0	4	0	8	0	0	0
JASMINE	300	0	0	0	0	0	162	0	0	19	0	96	0	0	0
SEASONAL FLOWER	132	0	0	0	0	0	399	17	0	17	0	19	0	0	0
OTHERS	71	0	0	0	0	0	7	30	0	19	0	25	0	0	0

Sources:

1. Different issues of “Estimates of area and production of principle crops” in West Bengal, Directorate of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal.
2. CMIE Report (various issues).

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Table 3B.
Compound Growth Rates (%) of Area of High Value Crops of Districts of West Bengal between the periods 1997 – 98 to 2004 – 05 (Graphical presentation)

Sources:

1. Different issues of “Estimates of area and production of principle crops” in West Bengal, Directorate of Agriculture, Government of West Bengal.
2. CMIE Report (various issues).

6. Conclusion

Crop diversification or crop shift is a new paradigm of sustainable agriculture. Crop diversification is not only a shift from traditional and less remunerative crops to more remunerative crops but it is a demand driven, need based situation specific and national goal seeking continuous and dynamic concept and involves spatial, temporal, value addition and resource complementary approaches. However, crop substitution and addition of more crops in existing cropping system has been the major

approach of diversification in India. The nature of crop diversification has been mainly from low value coarse cereals to high value oilseeds and other food grains.

Persistent low level of farmers' income may cause serious adverse effect on the future of agriculture in the country. To secure agriculture and to improve the livelihood of the people, adequate attention should be given to improve the welfare of the farmers and to raise agricultural income. New production technologies should be adopted and new varieties of crops should be produced. It will improve the cropping system by increasing yields, improving drought resilience, boosting resistance to pests and diseases. So there will be an opportunity to capture new market. It is needed to identify crops and varieties that may suit to a range of environments and farmer's preferences. Crop diversification is very helpful for the farmers. It provides better conditions for food security and enables farmers to grow surplus products for sale at market. So it helps to obtain more income to meet their requirements. Crop diversification also enables the farmers to gain access to national and international markets for new products, food and medicinal plants.

Endnotes :

- ¹ Saumya Chakrabarti and Anirban Kundu, 'Rural non-farm economy: A note on the impact of crop diversification and land conservation in India', *Economic and Political Weekly* 44.12 (March 21 – 27, 2009):69-75.
- ² CMIE Report (various issues).
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- ⁵ Raj Kumar Kundu and Apurba Kumar Chattopadhyay, 'Spatio-temporal variations of crop diversification – A Block level study in West Bengal', *Economic and Political Weekly* 53.21 (May 26, 2018): 58-64.